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Logarfmik funksiya qatnashgan murakkab tenglamalarni yechish usullari haqida

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Annotatsiya: Ko'p hollarda logarfmik tenglamalarga oid murakkabroq masalalarni yechish logarfmik funksiyalarning xossalarini yaxshi bilish bilan birga ularni o'z o'rnida qo'llay olishni talab etadi. Bunda tenglamalarni yechishning mavjud metodlari va almashtirish formulalarini qo'llash orqali berilgan tenglamani algebraik tenglamaga keltirish muhim masaladir. Ushbu maqolada murakkablik darajasi yuqori bo'lgan mavzuga oid ba'zi tenglamalarni yechish masalalari o'rganilgan bo'lib, matematikaga layoqatli o'quvchilar, talabalar va yosh o'qituvchilarga mavzu doirasida uslubiy ko'rsatmalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Logarfmik funksiya, teskari funksiya, aniqlanish sohasi, monotonlik, tenglama, ildiz, yechim, simmetriya, soddalashtirish, xossalar, taqqoslash metodi, logarifmlash, almashtirish, asos.

About the methods of solving complex equations in which the logarithmic function is involved

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Abstract: In most cases, solving more complex tables related to logarfmic equations requires a good knowledge of the properties of logarfmic functions and the ability to apply them in their place. In this case, it is important to bring the given equation to the algebraic equation by using the existing methods of solving equations and the substitution formulas. In this article, the problems of solving some equations on a subject with a high degree of complexity are studied, and students, students and young teachers who are worthy of mathematics, are given methodological instructions within the framework of the topic.

Keywords: logarithmic function, inverse function, area of detection, monotony, equation, root, solution, symmetry, simplification, properties, method of comparison, logarithmic, substitution, basis.

Ma'lumki, bugungi kunda barcha soha va yo'nalishlar bo'yicha malakali kadrlar tayyorlashda va raqamli iqtisodiyotga o'tishda matematik bilimlarga tayanilmoqda. Puxta matematik tayyorgarlikka ega bo'lish esa ta'limning maktab, akademik litsey va oliy ta'lim muassasalari matematika dasturlarini yaxshi o'zlashtirishga bog'liqdir. Shuning uchun ta'lim tizimida bir qancha tarixiy qarorlar qabul qilindi va uning asosida keng ko'lamli islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Jumladan, Prezidentimiz Sh.M.Mirziyoyevning 2020 yil 7 maydagi "Matematika sohasidagi ta'lim sifatini oshirish va ilmiy tadqiqotlarni rivojlantirish chora tadbirlari to'g'risida" nomli PQ-4708 qarori [1]da - Ta'limning barcha bosqichlarida matematika fanini o'qitish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish va matematika sohasidagi ta'lim sifatini oshirish bo'yicha dolzarb vazifalar belgilab berilgan.

Matematikaga iqtidorli ta'lim oluvchilarning turli xil misol va masalalarni yechish metodlaridan [2-5] ratsional foydalana olishlari ular matematik qobiliyati va madaniyatini shakllantirib borishga, matematika mashg'ulotlarida olgan bilim va ko'nikmalarni takomillashtirishga yordam beradi. Ushbu maqolada ijodiy faollik mustaqil fikrlash orqali bilimlarni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan murakkablik darajasiga ko'ra qiyinroq masalalarni, shu jumladan, logarifmik tenglamalarni yechish masalalari va usullari o'rganiladi.

1- masala. $\sqrt{2\log_8(-x)} - \log_8 \sqrt{x^2} = 0$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Dastlab berilgan tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasini qaraymiz.

$$\begin{cases} 2\log_8(-x) \geq 0 \\ -x > 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x \leq -1 \\ x < 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow x \leq -1 .$$

Endi berilgan tenglamaning yechimini topamiz. Ma'lumki, $\sqrt{x^2} = |x|$. Bundan $\sqrt{2\log_8(-x)} - \log_8 |x| = 0$. Tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasi $x \leq -1$ bo'lganligi uchun $|x| = -x$ bo'lib tenglamani $\sqrt{2\log_8(-x)} - \log_8(-x) = 0$ ko'rinishda yozish mumkin. $\log_8(-x) = a$ belgilashni kiritsak $\sqrt{2a} - a = 0$ yoki $a = \sqrt{2a}$ bo'lib, kvadratga ko'tarsak $a^2 = 2a$, bundan esa $a_1 = 0$ va $a_2 = 2$ kelib chiqadi. Demak, masala $\log_8(-x) = 0$ va $\log_8(-x) = 2$ tenglamalarni yechishga keltirildi. Bularni yechib $x_1 = -1$ va $x_2 = -64$ berilgan tenglamaning ildizlarini topamiz.

2-masala. $\log_4(6 + \sqrt{x} - |\sqrt{x} - 2|) = 0,5 + \log_2|\sqrt{x} - |\sqrt{x} - 2||$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Berilgan tenglamani yechish uchun quyidagi belgilashni kiritamiz:
 $\sqrt{x} - |\sqrt{x} - 2| = a$. U holda $\log_4(6+a) = 0,5 + \log_2|a|$ tenglamani hosil qilamiz. Bu tenglamani yechish uchun quyidagi xossalardan foydalanamiz:

$$\log_{a^n} b = \frac{1}{n} \log_a b = \log_a b^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (1) \quad \log_a b - \log_a c = \log_a \left(\frac{b}{c}\right) \quad (2)$$

(1) xossaga ko'ra:

$$\log_{2^2}(6+a) = 0,5 + \log_2|a| \quad \text{yoki} \quad \log_2(6+a)^{\frac{1}{2}} = 0,5 + \log_2|a| \quad \text{yoki}$$

$$\log_2 \sqrt{a+6} - \log_2|a| = 0,5 \quad \text{bo'lib, (2) xossaga asosan:}$$

$$\log_2 \frac{\sqrt{a+6}}{|a|} = 0,5 \quad \text{yoki} \quad \frac{\sqrt{a+6}}{|a|} = \sqrt{2} \quad \text{yoki} \quad \sqrt{a+6} = \sqrt{2}|a| \quad \text{hosil bo'ladi. Oxirgi}$$

tenglikning ikki tamoni kvadratga ko'tarib $a+6 = 2a^2$ yoki $2a^2 - a - 6 = 0$ kvadrat tenglamaga kelamiz. Uning yechimi $a_1 = 2$ va $a_2 = -\frac{3}{2}$. Demak, $\sqrt{x} - |\sqrt{x} - 2| = 2$ va $\sqrt{x} - |\sqrt{x} - 2| = -\frac{3}{2}$ ekan. Ya'ni

$$1) \sqrt{x} - |\sqrt{x} - 2| = 2 \quad \text{yoki} \quad |\sqrt{x} - 2| = \sqrt{x} - 2 \quad \text{bundan} \quad \sqrt{x} - 2 \geq 0 \quad \text{va} \quad x \geq 4;$$

$$2) \sqrt{x} - |\sqrt{x} - 2| = -\frac{3}{2} \quad \text{yoki} \quad |\sqrt{x} - 2| = \sqrt{x} + \frac{3}{2}. \quad \text{Ma'lumki tenglamaning yechimi} \quad x = \frac{1}{16}$$

Endi berilgan tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasini topamiz:

$$\begin{cases} 6 + \sqrt{x} - |\sqrt{x} - 2| > 0 \\ x \geq 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} |\sqrt{x} - 2| < 6 + \sqrt{x} \\ x \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

Bu sistema x ning istalgan musbat qiymatida o'rinli. Demak, aniqlanish sohasi $x \in [0; \infty)$. U holda berilgan tenglamaning yechimi $\left\{\frac{1}{16}\right\} \cup [4; \infty)$ boladi.

3-masala. $\sqrt{\log_x(\sqrt{3x})} \cdot \log_3 x = -1$ tenglamani yeching.

Yechish: Ushbu tenglamani yechish uchun logarifmning quyidagi xossalaridan foydalanamiz:

$$\log_a(b \cdot c) = \log_a b + \log_a c \quad (3), \quad \log_a b^n = n \log_a b \quad (4), \quad \log_a a = 1 \quad (5), \quad \log_a b = \frac{1}{\log_b a} \quad (6).$$

Berilgan tenglamada dastlab ildiz ostidagi ifodani yoyib chiqamiz:

$$\sqrt{\log_x(\sqrt{3} \cdot \sqrt{x})} \cdot \log_3 x = -1. \quad \text{Endi (3) xossaga ko'ra} \quad \sqrt{\log_x(\sqrt{3} \cdot \sqrt{x})} \cdot \log_3 x = -1,$$

$\sqrt{\log_x \sqrt{3} + \log_x \sqrt{x}} \cdot \log_3 x = -1$ yoki $\sqrt{\log_x 3^{\frac{1}{2}} + \log_x x^{\frac{1}{2}}} \cdot \log_3 x = -1$ ni hosil qilamiz. Bundan

(4) tenglikga ko'ra $\sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \log_x 3 + \frac{1}{2} \log_x x} \cdot \log_3 x = -1$ ga kelamiz. Endi (5) xossadan

foydalansak, $\sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \log_x 3 + \frac{1}{2}} \cdot \log_3 x = -1$ yoki $\sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \log_x 3 + \frac{1}{2}} = -\frac{1}{\log_3 x}$ ni hosil qilamiz.

So'ngra (6) ga asosan esa $\sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \log_x 3 + \frac{1}{2}} = -\log_3 3$ tenglamaga ega bo'lamiz. Oxirgi

tenglamada $\log_x 3 = a$ deb belgilash kiritsak, $\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(a+1)} = -a$ irratsional tenglama hosil

bo'ladi. Uni yechamiz: $\frac{1}{2}(a+1) = a^2$, $a^2 - \frac{1}{2}a - \frac{1}{2} = 0$. Bundan $a_1 = 1$ va $a_2 = -\frac{1}{2}$ ni

topamiz va $\log_x 3 = 1$ va $\log_x 3 = -\frac{1}{2}$ tenglamalarni yechib (bunda $\begin{cases} x \neq 1 \\ x > 0 \end{cases}$) $x_1 = 3$ va

$x_2 = \frac{1}{9}$ ildizlarni topamiz. Berilgan tenglama x ning qanday qiymatlarida ma'no-ga ega bo'lishini quyidagi sistemani yechish orqali aniqlaymiz:

$$\begin{cases} \log_x \sqrt{3x} > 0 \\ \log_3 x < 0 \\ x > 0 \\ x \neq 1 \end{cases}.$$

a) $\log_x \sqrt{3x} > 0$, $\log_x \sqrt{3} + \log_x \sqrt{x} > 0$ va yuqoridagidek almashtirishlar bilan

$\frac{1}{2}(\log_x 3 + 1) > 0$ yoki $\log_x 3 > -1$ ni hosil qilamiz. Bu tengsizlik $0 < x < 1$ bo'lganda $3 < \frac{1}{x}$ yoki $x < \frac{1}{3}$ bo'lib yechimi $x \in (0, \frac{1}{3})$, $x > 1$ bo'lganda esa $3 > \frac{1}{x}$ yoki $x > \frac{1}{3}$ bo'lib yechim $x \in (1; \infty)$.

b) $\log_3 x < 0$ da yechim $0 < x < 1$. Demak umumiy holda sistema yechimi ya'ni tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasi $(0, \frac{1}{3})$ dan iborat.

Natijada berilgan tenglama yechimi $x = \frac{1}{9}$ ekanligini ko'ramiz.

$$\sqrt{x - 2\sqrt{x-1}} + \sqrt{x + 2\sqrt{x-1}} = \log_{\frac{1}{2}}(x-1)$$

4-masala.

Yechish: Avvalo tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasini qaraymiz.

$$\begin{cases} x - 2\sqrt{x-1} \geq 0 \\ x + 2\sqrt{x-1} \geq 0 \\ x - 1 > 0 \end{cases} \text{ . Bu sistema } x > 1 \text{ bo'lganda doimo o'rinli.}$$

Demak tenglamaning aniqlanish sohasi: $x > 1$

Endi tenglamaning chap tamoni, ya'ni $(1; +\infty)$ da ifodani soddalashtiramiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{x-1} - 2\sqrt{x-1} + 1 + \sqrt{x-1} + 2\sqrt{x-1} + 1 &= \sqrt{(\sqrt{x-1}-1)^2} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{x-1}+1)^2} = \\ |\sqrt{x-1}-1| + |\sqrt{x-1}+1| &= |\sqrt{x-1}-1| + \sqrt{x-1} + 1 \end{aligned}$$

Bu yerda modul ostidagi $\sqrt{x-1}-1$ ifoda $x > 2$ da $\sqrt{x-1}-1$ ga, $1 < x < 2$ da esa $1-\sqrt{x-1}$ ga teng bo'ladi. Shuning uchun tenglamani ikkita holat bo'yicha qaraymiz.

$$1) \ 1 < x < 2 \text{ bo'lsa } \quad 1 - \sqrt{x-1} + \sqrt{x-1} + 1 = \log_{\frac{1}{2}}(x-1) \quad \log_{\frac{1}{2}}(x-1) = 2 \quad \text{bundan} \quad \log_{\frac{1}{2}}(x-1) = 2 \quad \text{va} \quad x = \frac{5}{4}$$

$$2) \ x > 2 \text{ bo'lsa } \quad \sqrt{x-1} - 1 + \sqrt{x-1} + 1 = \log_{\frac{1}{2}}(x-1) \quad \text{Bundan } \log_2(x-1) = -2\sqrt{x-1} \text{ bo'lib,}$$

aniqlanish sohasiga ko'ra doimo $x > 1$ bo'lishi kerak, tenglamaning o'ng tamoni esa doimo manfiy son bo'ladi. Shuning uchun bu tenglama yechimga ega emas.

Natijada, qaralayotgan tenglama yagona $x = \frac{5}{4}$ yechimga ega ekanlini ko'ramiz.

Xulosa o'rnida aytishimiz mumkinki, murakkablik darajasi yuqori bo'lgan masalalarni o'rganish, jumladan, mazkur maqolada keltirilgan logarifmik tenglamalarni yechish asosida asosiy metodlarni va almashtirish formulalarini kengaytirish yotishini anglash qiyinmas. Bu jarayonda sonning logarifmi va logarifmik funksiyaning xossalari o'z ornida to'g'ri qo'llay olish muhim bo'lib, olingan bilimlarni mustahkamlash orqali u yoki bu masalalarni yecha bilish malakasi rivojlanadi. Matematikaning boshqa mavzulariga oid murakkab masalalar ham ko'p uchraydi, ma'lum muddatda ularni yechishni muntazam davom ettirish matematik qobiliyatni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi[5-16].

Parametrlil logarifmik tenglamalarni yechish masalalari jarayonida quyidagi ishlar ketma-ketligiga e'tibor qaratish lozim

1) parametrlil logarifmik tenglamalarni yechish masalalari parametr qatnashmagan logarifmik tenglamalarni yechishdan masalani yechish jarayonida parametrga nisbatan hosil qilinadigan tenglamani yechish natijasida, shu parametr qabul qilishi mumkin bo'lgan qiymatlari ichidan yechimni izlash bilan farq qiladi.

2) maqolada ba'zi parametrlil logarifmik tenglamalarga oid masalalar va ularni yechish usullarini bayon qilish, keltirish orqali o'quvchilarning mavzu bo'yicha bilimlari darajasini mustahkamlash va kengaytirish hamda bilimlarni tadqiqot

faoliyatida murakkabligi ortib borayotgan muammoli masalalarni yechishga qo'llash orqali chuqurlashtirishga erishish mumkin.

3) o'qitishning maqsadlaridan biri - o'quvchilarga matematikaga bo'lgan qiziqishining ahamiyatini tushuntirish va ularning imkoniyatlarini baholash ekanligidan kelib chiqib, ular majburiy murakkablik darajasiga nisbatan yuqori muammolarni hal qilishni, erkin foydalanish darajasida bir qator texnik va intellektual qobiliyatlarni egallashni o'rganishdan iborat.

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